

Synthesis of spirocyclic compounds : A photochemical approach

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Manuscript received 18 August 2008, accepted 12 November 2008

Abstract : The phototransformations of 2-thienyl-3-cycloalkenyloxy benzopyrans in benzene lead to fused spirocyclic compounds bearing thiophene ring system.

Keywords : Spiropyran, photoirradiation, type-II reaction, cycloalkenyloxychromone.

Introduction

Spirocyclic compounds have been known for a long time to be present in phytochemicals¹ and exhibit a variety of biological activities such as antitumour, antimicrobial, antibiotic agents, antagonists, antidepressant and antidiabetics etc.²⁻⁹. These compounds, particularly spiropyrans find practical application in display and photochromic memory systems¹⁰⁻¹⁵. Synthetic methods of spirocyclic compounds involve thermal cyclisation¹⁶, cycloadditions¹⁷, eliminations¹⁸ and various other synthon approaches that are specific to a particular compound or a particular class of compounds. A few reports are available in literature on photochemical synthesis of these compounds¹⁹. Recently a new route to spiropyrans through photochemical γ -H abstraction has been developed in our

laboratory^{20,21}. To further extend this synthetic route, here we report the photochemical synthesis of some new spiropyrans bearing thiophene ring system.

Results and discussion

The compounds **3** and **4** required for the photochemical synthesis of spirocyclics were obtained through the alkylations of appropriate 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyrans²² with suitable bromocycloalkenes (Scheme 1).

Photoirradiation of benzene solution of compound **3a-3e** and **4a-4b** under N₂ atmosphere with 125 W Hg vapour lamp through Pyrex filter afforded benzospiropyrans **5a-5e** and **6a-6b** respectively in 20-40% yields (Scheme 2).

The structure of photoproducts **5a-5e** and **6a-6b** was

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 3-cycloalkenyloxy-2-thienylbenzopyrans.

Scheme 2. Photolysis of benzopyrans 3a-3e and 4a-4b.

confirmed by their IR, NMR and Mass spectral data (Experimental section). The mass spectrum of compound 5a showed the m/z 384 as base peak pointing out the loss of two mass units in its formation from 3a. The other prominent ions were located at m/z 154 and 230 (rDA). The rDA fragments produced by the fission through ring B are characteristic features of these types of compounds and were also observed in compounds 5b-5e. Here in cycloalkenyloxy benzopyrans 3a-3e and 4a-4b, the formation of spiropyran is accompanied by the loss of two mass units and in spite of our best efforts (examination of TLC, photolysate ^1H NMR) no dihydro product²⁰ could be detected. Mechanistically, the formation of photoproducts is through the biradical A that is generated by the favourable abstraction of γ -H from cycloalkenyloxy group by the photoexcited^{22,23} C=O through six-membered cyclic T.S. (Scheme 3). This biradical undergoes a bond formation with thiophene followed by the elimination of two hydrogens.

cleavage of C-H bond. Many similar studies²³ have proved that such dehydrogenations take place without the addition of any oxidant. When furan²¹ was present at C-2 in benzopyrans, only photocyclised products (dihydro) were obtained along with some secondary fused cyclopropyl products. For such structural/substituent difference, the only assignable reason could be the variation in electron density on the ring moiety at C-2. As the electron density on the ring at C-2 decreases from furyl to thienyl, the formation of cyclodehydrogenated product becomes prominent. It is also possible that the removal of hydrogen from B is faster than its tautomerisation as the former leads to the formation of more stable aromatic (cyclodehydrogenated) products as depicted in Scheme 3. The yields of all the spirocyclic photoproducts are similar irrespective of ring size ($n = 1-4$) variation of cycloalkene at 3-position.

It may be concluded that the synthesis of spiropyrans can be effectively carried out by the Norrish type II pho-

Scheme 3. Mechanism of photochemical spiropyran formation

Here, the elimination of two hydrogens has occurred in the absence of an oxidant (I_2 and O_2 etc.) as the reaction has been carried out under oxygen free nitrogen atmosphere (99.9%). In the photocyclisation of stilbenes and phenanthrenes, such dehydrogenations has been rationalised to occur through vibrationally excited hot ground state intermediates²⁴⁻²⁶ which lose energy through

rereaction in benzopyrans. This method offers a convenient, safer and eco-friendly route for the synthesis of fused ring spirocyclic compounds.

Experimental

General : IR spectra were recorded on a Buck Scientific 500 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. ^1H NMR

spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz Bruker spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Elemental analysis was carried on Perkin-Elmer 2400 instrument. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. TLC plates were coated with silica gel G (suspended in CHCl_3 -MeOH) and iodine vapours were used as visualizing agent. Silica gel 100-200 mesh was used for column chromatography. All photochemical reactions were conducted under a nitrogen (99.9%) atmosphere. Any trace of oxygen and moisture from the procured nitrogen was removed by passing through alkaline pyragalol solution and concentrated sulphuric acid respectively.

General method for the synthesis of 6-chloro-3-cyclooctenyloxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 3a :

A suspension of 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-one **1** (2.8 g, 0.01 mol), cyclooctenyl bromide (1.89 g, 0.01 mol), freshly heated anhydrous K_2CO_3 (1.0 g) and tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide (50 mg) in dry acetone (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h with stirring. A subsequent filtration of the reaction mixture followed by distillation of the solvent yielded a light yellow solid that was percolated through a column of silica-gel (100-120 mesh) using petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) as eluent and further crystallized from ethanol to afford **3a**.

The other substrates **3b-3e** and **4a-4b** were synthesized by reacting differently substituted 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4H-chromen-4-ones and a suitable cycloalkenyl bromide using the same procedure.

Compound 3a. Yield 53%, white solid; m.p. 142-143 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1640 (C=O), 1601 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.19 (1H, d, J_{m} 2.4 Hz, H-5), 8.02 (1H, dd, $J_{3',5'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.58 (1H, dd, $J_{5',4'}$ 4.8 Hz, $J_{5',3'}$ 1.2 Hz, H-5'), 7.56 (1H, dd, $J_{\text{m},0}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.50 (1H, d, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-8), 7.23 (1H, dd, $J_{4',5'}$ 4.8 Hz, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-4'), 6.15-6.10 (1H, m, H-3''), 5.62-5.54 (2H, m, H-1'',2''), 2.27-1.54 (10H, m, H-4'',5'',6'',7'',8''); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 23.76 (C-7''), 25.98 (C-4''), 26.21 (C-5''), 29.16 (C-6''), 35.69 (C-8''), 78.74 (C-1''), 119.38 (C-8), 125.07 (C-10), 125.16 (C-3'), 127.32 (C-4'), 129.85 (C-2), 130.41 (C-6), 131.11 (C-3), 131.19 (C-5'), 131.31 (C-2''), 131.98 (C-3''), 133.32 (C-5), 136.44 (C-7), 146.95 (C-2'), 152.99 (C-9), 172.93 (C-4); MS (EI) : m/z 386 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 65.12; H, 4.96. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{ClO}_3\text{S}$: C, 65.19; H, 4.95%).

Compound 3b. Yield 58%, white solid; m.p. 96-98

°C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1632 (C=O), 1601 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.09 (1H, s, H-5), 7.90 (1H, dd, $J_{3',5'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.50 (1H, dd, $J_{5',3'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{5',4'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.34 (1H, s, H-8), 7.10 (1H, dd, $J_{4',5'}$ 4.8 Hz, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-4'), 5.86-5.76 (2H, m, H-2'',3''), 5.42-5.40 (1H, m, H-1''), 2.45 (3H, s, C_7 - CH_3), 2.02-1.87 (4H, m, H-4'',5''); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 18.98 (C_7 - CH_3), 21.78 (C-4'), 25.01 (C-5''), 74.38 (C-1''), 117.49 (C-8), 123.01 (C-10), 124.83 (C-3'), 127.45 (C-4'), 128.03 (C-2), 129.79 (C-3), 130.94 (C-6), 131.28 (C-5'), 131.91 (C-5), 135.26 (C-2'',3''), 141.09 (C-2'), 150.76 (C-7), 152.94 (C-9), 172.12 (C-4); MS (EI) : m/z 358 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 63.52; H, 4.20. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClO}_3\text{S}$: C, 63.59; H, 4.21%).

Compound 3c. Yield 60%, white solid; m.p. 167-169 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1633 (C=O), 1600 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.19 (1H, s, H-5), 8.00 (1H, dd, $J_{3',5'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.59 (1H, dd, $J_{5',3'}$ 1.2 Hz, $J_{5',4'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.43 (1H, s, H-8), 7.20 (1H, dd, $J_{4',5'}$ 4.8 Hz, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-4'), 5.95-5.85 (2H, m, H-2'',3''), 5.51-5.49 (1H, m, H-1''), 2.53 (3H, s, C_7 - CH_3), 2.11-1.94 (6H, m, H-4'',5'',6''); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 19.58 (C_7 - CH_3), 20.78 (C-5''), 25.01 (C-4''), 29.01 (C-6''), 75.38 (C-1''), 119.49 (C-8), 123.21 (C-10), 125.33 (C-3'), 127.28 (C-4'), 129.93 (C-2), 130.97 (C-3), 131.04 (C-6), 131.28 (C-5'), 132.21 (C-5), 136.51 (C-2'',3''), 142.39 (C-2'), 151.61 (C-7), 152.94 (C-9), 173.12 (C-4); MS (EI) : m/z 372 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 64.50; H, 4.56. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClO}_3\text{S}$: C, 64.42; H, 4.60%).

Compound 3d. Yield 60%, white solid; m.p. 96-97 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1643 (C=O), 1605 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.02 (2H, m, H-5,3'), 7.58 (1H, dd, $J_{5',4'}$ 4.8 Hz, $J_{5',3'}$ 1.2 Hz, H-5'), 7.50 (1H, dd, $J_{\text{m},0}$ 2.4, 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.43 (1H, d, J_0 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.20 (1H, dd, $J_{4',5'}$ 4.8 Hz, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-4'), 5.97-5.85 (2H, m, H-3'',2''), 5.49 (1H, m, H-1''), 2.48 (3H, s, C_6 - CH_3), 2.08-1.94 (6H, m, H-4'',5'',6''); MS (EI) : m/z 338 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 71.05; H, 5.33. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 70.98; H, 5.36%).

Compound 3e. Yield 52%, white solid; m.p. 112-114 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1637 (C=O), 1606 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.13 (1H, d, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-5), 7.99 (1H, d, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.57 (1H, d, $J_{5',4'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.16 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-4'), 6.98 (1H, dd, $J_{\text{m},0}$ 1.5, 9.0 Hz, H-6), 6.92 (1H, d, J_{m} 1.5 Hz, H-8), 5.97-5.84 (2H, m, H-2'',3''), 5.94-5.90 (1H, m, H-1''), 3.94 (3H, s, C_7 - OCH_3), 2.08-1.83 (6H, m, H-4'',5'',6''); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 18.60 (C-5''), 23.50 (C-4''), 28.20 (C-6''), 54.91 (C_7 - OCH_3), 74.68 (C-1''), 98.87 (C-8), 113.94 (C-6), 117.91 (C-10),

125.03 (C-3'), 126.98 (C-4'), 127.23 (C-2), 128.67 (C-3), 129.40 (C-5'), 130.32 (C-5), 135.83 (C-2'',3''), 141.36 (C-2'), 151.07 (C-9), 162.06 (C-7), 172.80 (C-4); MS (EI) : m/z 354 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 67.77; H, 5.08. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{18}O_4S$: C, 67.78; H, 5.12%).

Compound **4a**. Yield 2.4 g (60%), white solid; m.p. 132–133 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1637 (C=O), 1602 (C=C); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.19 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.82 (1H, d, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.58 (1H, dd, $J_{m,0}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.45 (1H, d, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-8), 6.90 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.9 Hz, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, H-4'), 6.15–6.12 (1H, m, H-3''), 5.62–5.56 (2H, m, H-1'',2''), 2.60 (3H, s, $C_{5''}$ -CH₃), 2.28–1.50 (10H, m, H-4'',5'',6'',7'',8''); $\delta^{13}C$ 14.39 ($C_{5''}$ -CH₃), 22.70 (C-7''), 24.92 (C-4''), 25.13 (C-5''), 28.10 (C-6''), 34.59 (C-8''), 77.48 (C-1''), 118.19 (C-8), 124.92 (C-10), 128.40 (C-3'), 129.20 (C-4'), 129.25 (C-2), 129.90 (C-6), 130.27 (C-3), 131.24 (C-5), 132.04 (C-2'',3''), 134.78 (C-2'), 145.71 (C-7), 151.06 (C-5'), 151.88 (C-9), 171.70 (C-4); MS (EI) : m/z 400 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 65.82; H, 5.27. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{21}ClO_3S$: C, 65.91; H, 5.28%).

Compound **4b**. Yield 65%, pale yellow solid; m.p. 120–122 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1633 (C=O), 1599 (C=C); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.17 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.82 (1H, d, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.6 Hz, H-3'), 7.58 (1H, dd, $J_{m,0}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.45 (1H, d, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-8), 6.86 (1H, dd, J_{allyl} 0.9 Hz, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.6 Hz, H-4'), 5.93–5.84 (2H, m, H-3'',2''), 5.45 (1H, m, H-1''), 2.57 (3H, s, $C_{5''}$ -CH₃), 2.10–1.57 (6H, m, H-4'',5'',6''); MS (EI) : m/z 372 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 64.28; H, 4.59. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{17}ClO_3S$: C, 64.42; H, 4.60%).

Photolysis of 6-chloro-3-cyclooctenyloxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 3a :

General procedure : A deoxygenated solution of chromone **3a** (200 mg) in dry thiophene free benzene (150 ml) was refluxed for 5 min. The solution was outgassed with nitrogen for 1 h and then irradiated in a Pyrex reactor under nitrogen atmosphere for 60 min with a 125 W Hg vapor lamp. The removal of solvent under reduced pressure yielded a red gummy mass that was chromatographed over a column of silica gel to yield **3a** and **5a**.

Other compounds **3b-3e** and **4a-4b** were also photolysed by following the same procedure to yield respective spirocyclic compounds as photoproducts.

Compound **5a**. Yield 35%, white solid; m.p. 166–168 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1645 (C=O), 1603 (C=C); δ_H ($CDCl_3$)

8.18 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.50 (1H, dd, $J_{m,0}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-9), 7.47 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.8 Hz, H-2), 7.39 (1H, d, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-10), 6.84 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.8 Hz, H-3), 5.78–5.63 (2H, m, H-2',3'), 2.79–2.76 (1H, m, H-4'), 2.49–2.46 (1H, m, H-4'), 2.38–1.83 (8H, m, H-5',6',7',8'); MS (EI) : m/z 384 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 65.46; H, 4.41. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{17}ClO_3S$: C, 65.53; H, 4.45%).

Compound **5b**. Yield 30%, white solid; m.p. 161–163 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1640 (C=O), 1595 (C=C); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.24 (1H, s, H-7), 7.54 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.8 Hz, H-2), 7.41 (1H, s, H-10), 6.88 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.8 Hz, H-3), 6.20–6.14 (1H, m, H-3'), 6.01 (1H, d, $J_{2',3'}$ 9.9 Hz, H-2'), 2.50 (3H, s, C_9 -CH₃), 2.38–2.01 (4H, m, H-4',5'); MS (EI) : m/z 356 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 63.82; H, 3.69. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{13}ClO_3S$: C, 63.95; H, 3.67%).

Compound **5c**. Yield 38%, white solid; m.p. 178–180 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1640 (C=O), 1596 (C=C); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.26 (1H, s, H-7), 7.54 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.8 Hz, H-2), 7.42 (1H, s, H-10), 6.89 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.8 Hz, H-3), 6.19–6.14 (1H, m, H-3'), 6.02 (1H, d, $J_{2',3'}$ 9.9 Hz, H-2'), 2.51 (3H, s, C_9 -CH₃), 2.38–1.98 (6H, m, H-4',5',6'); $\delta^{13}C$ 20.08 (C_9 -CH₃), 22.98 (C-5'), 28.01 (C-4'), 34.01 (C-6'), 74.05 (C-4), 119.79 (C-10), 123.22 (C-12), 125.90 (C-3), 127.09 (C-13), 129.93 (C-14), 130.06 (C-8), 130.84 (C-7), 131.23 (C-2), 131.98 (C-15), 136.50 (C-2',3'), 142.09 (C-16), 151.34 (C-9), 152.66 (C-11), 174.02 (C-6); MS (EI) : m/z 370 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 64.71; H, 4.10. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{15}ClO_3S$: C, 64.77; H, 4.08%).

Compound **5d**. Yield 21%, pale yellow solid; m.p. 166–168 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1638 (C=O), 1595 (C=C); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.08 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.55 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.8 Hz, H-2), 7.48 (1H, dd, $J_{m,0}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-9), 7.38 (1H, d, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-10), 6.80 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.8 Hz, H-3), 6.09–6.06 (1H, m, H-3'), 5.93 (1H, d, $J_{2',3'}$ 9.9 Hz, H-2'), 2.37 (3H, s, C_9 -CH₃), 2.33–1.86 (6H, m, H-4',5',6'); MS (EI) : m/z 336 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 71.30; H, 4.83. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{16}O_3S$: C, 71.41; H, 4.79%).

Compound **5e**. Yield 24%, yellow solid; m.p. 176–178 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1643 (C=O), 1601 (C=C); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.12 (1H, d, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.42 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.8 Hz, H-2), 6.90 (1H, dd, J_m 2.4 Hz, J_0 9.0 Hz, H-8), 6.85 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-10), 6.80 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.8 Hz, H-3), 6.13–6.02 (1H, m, H-3'), 5.94 (1H, d, $J_{2',3'}$ 9.9 Hz, H-2'), 3.82 (3H, s, C_9 -OCH₃), 2.41–1.73 (6H, m, H-4',5',6'); MS (EI) : m/z 352 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 68.22; H, 4.56. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{16}O_4S$: C, 68.16; H, 4.58%).

Compound **6a**. Yield 39%, white solid; m.p. 163–165 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1645 (C=O), 1605 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.25 (1H, d, J_{m} 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.56 (1H, dd, $J_{\text{m,o}}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-9), 7.45 (1H, d, J_{o} 9.0 Hz, H-10), 6.60 (1H, s, H-3), 5.85–5.75 (2H, m, H-2',3'), 2.58 (3H, s, C₂'-CH₃), 2.19–2.16 (1H, m, H-4'), 2.09–2.04 (1H, m, H-4'), 1.88–1.53 (8H, m, H-5',6',7',8'); MS (EI) : m/z 398 (M⁺, 100%) (Found : C, 66.19; H, 4.76. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₉ClO₃S : C, 66.24; H, 4.80%).

Compound **6b**. Yield 28%, yellowish solid; m.p. 185–188 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1641 (C=O), 1604 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.26 (1H, d, J_{m} 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.54 (1H, dd, $J_{\text{m,o}}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-9), 7.46 (1H, d, J_{o} 9.0 Hz, H-10), 6.57 (1H, s, H-3), 6.15 (1H, td, $J_{2',3'}$ 9.6 Hz, $J_{3',4'}$ 5.8 Hz, H-3'), 5.95 (1H, d, $J_{2',3'}$ 9.6 Hz, H-2'), 2.55 (3H, s, C₂-CH₃), 2.41–1.77 (6H, m, H-4',5',6'); MS (EI) : m/z 370 (M⁺, 100%) (Found : C, 64.61; H, 4.03. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅ClO₃S : C, 64.77; H, 4.08%).

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